

POINTS OF INTEREST ALONG THE GREENWAY

Angimbè woods

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The Angimbè woods, about 4 km north of Calatafimi Segesta, is one of the most charming nature spots in this region. Larger than 200 hectares, this wonderful, wide green area allows visitors to experience unspoiled nature. It is a perfect place for hiking and trekking near Calatafimi Segesta. Large shrubs along the pathways lead through this scenic forested area. Guided tours and workshops are available, ranging from promoting this wonderful place to raising environmental awareness, and classes that further explore botany and mycology. There are several great spots for picnics, playgrounds for children, and campfire areas. The Angimbè woods' fauna is rich, and includes several species such as mammals, amphibians, and a large presence of migratory birds. This is a perfect place for birdwatchers. It is also home to more than 700 botanical species, including cork oaks, holm oaks, and some indigenous plants, exclusively found in this area.

Segesta Archaeological Park Shrine in Contrada Mango

Among the ancient and classical sacred areas of the city, there was not only the shrine on the western hill, with a large Doric temple, but also the **non-urban shrine in Contrada Mango**, the ruins of which can still be visible when walking the path. This shrine lies on the southeastern slopes of Mount Barbaro, in a highly remarkable naturalistic setting, and faces the Vallone della Fusa and the Gaggera River, which deeply shapes this sacred landscape. The sacred area was magnificent and imposing. Surrounded by a mighty boundary and terracing wall, a large Doric temple (28x56 m) loomed up. This peripteral building, surrounded by columns, featured a pronaos (vestibule), a cella (small chamber), and an opisthodomos (back chamber). The building, whose foundations still exist, is dated to the mid-fifth century BC or so, and its architecture style belongs to the Selinuntine culture. Actually, it was the first peripteral temple built by the Segestan community. The sacred area revealed Greek vases, local pottery, marble sculpture fragments, and metal objects, including several bronze and iron weapons. The shrine used to be visited by both men and women during individual or collective ceremonies. Unfortunately, it is still unknown the identity of the deity to whom it was consecrated.

It can be visited by accessing the Segesta Archaeological Park.

"Giardini del Kaggera"

These gardens preserve a number of irrigation systems' remains from the Islamic period, which provide evidence of a harmonious connection between nature and human action over the centuries. A place where silence reigns, and only the water flowing can be heard. The rural landscape is marked not only by gebbie (tanks) and cube (early Christian or Byzantine chapels), but also by the so called **zachie**, namely canals used to convey water from the Gaggera River to the nearby mills, and to guarantee water supply to irrigate the surrounding fields. The flow of water was controlled by means of a wooden valve, referred to in dialect as a "zappeddu."

A clever use of water can also be associated with the charming **flax wash house**. Once in use for washing clothes, it was eventually also used to steep flax, which was farmed in the Calatafimi countryside until the 1950s. Particularly fascinating is also the so-called **bocca della verità**, namely "mouth of truth", three natural openings in the mountain ridge that resemble the eyes and mouth of a mask.

Along this section of the trail, visitors can admire **centuries-old olive trees** and lush citrus groves, which are cultivated according to traditional practices, that produce the **Ovaletto di Calatafimi**. This oval-shaped, seedless pale orange, with a particularly scented peel, is a late cultivar ripening in spring. The Ovaletto has been included by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry in the list of Regional Traditional Food Products.

Zachie

Flax wash house

Bocca della verità

Ovaletto di Calatafimi

Ponte Patti station

The train station of Ponte Patti is a simple yet functional building that was designed to serve the present town of Calatafimi-Segesta. It still lies along the disused railway line. From this point, the city tour can begin.

Calatafimi Segesta town

Antica Trasversale Sicula and Via Francigena Mazarense roads

From this point, visitors can take the **Antica Trasversale Sicula**, a long route from Camarina to Mozia, and the **Via Francigena Mazarense**. These two routes, full of history and nature, disclose the abundance and cultural diversity of Sicily.

Contrada Canale trough

Troughs in Contrada Canale and Contrada Rio

Emblematic elements of ancient rural culture, troughs are stone or masonry tanks that stored water for herds, pack animals, and people crossing the countryside. Here, architectural features were in harmony with the landscape. Troughs were frequently used for irrigation purposes, but they also served as wash houses, in some cases. They could be paired with a fountain, or embellished with inscriptions, coats of arms, sculptures, and sacred subject figures. While simple in their shapes and materials used, troughs feature some efficient technical feats to convey water from the source, by taking advantage of its natural fall, and to let people draw it.

Along the disused railway, visitors find the troughs in Contrada Canale and Contrada Rio. The **Contrada Canale trough**, paired with a simple fountain, has a complex system of connected tanks and overflows, which poured water down the canal and then into the river. This outstanding example of water management is an Islamic heritage. The wall features a Madonna and Child bas relief type, which echoes the marble triptych iconography kept in the Church of the Madonna of Giubino in Calatafimi-Segesta. The Virgin Mary is deeply connected with the rural world. In fact, every year, on the second Sunday of July, the wooden simulacrum (vara, in dialect) of the Madonna is carried to her countryside shrine, where it remains until the third Sunday of September, which is when it returns to its city shrine. As for the imposing **trough in Contrada Rio**, its wall bears the date of 1948, which is the year it was built or, more likely, restored.

Five-arched bridge

Civil engineering work

Along the route, there are several architectural structures with operational purposes for the disused railway section, which engineering value is still preserved. Noteworthy are also the long blind arched stone **retaining wall**, the **five-arched bridge** with an iron railing and balconies with brick balustrades, which were built for safety reasons, and the **underpass** that still displays the fascio littorio roundel, and an inscription that indicates the year of construction, 1929.

Retaining wall

Underpass

Contrada Margi gypsum

This is a cycle II gypsum formation (Pasquasia gypsum), dating back to the uppermost Messinian stage. This selenitic macrocrystalline gypsum features a distinctive "spear-iron" twinning, immersed in a gypsarenitic and gypsum-pelitic matrix. This site is particularly significant from both a geological and environmental perspective. It is also home to raw material for the chalk industry, which mines are located near Pianto Romano.

Archpriest's Mill

The Archpriest's Mill is one of the most evocative places in the area of Calatafimi. The mill was restored by an individual, with the help of a grant from G.A.L. Elimos. It is a mill with a horizontal wheel, and is named after Antonio Brandi, the archpriest of Calatafimi between 1590 and 1661, founder of the Casa delle Orfane, to which he assigned the profit from his own mill, once called "Garamboli". It was part of a network of watermills built along the Gaggera River, supplied by a canal system (zachie), hence its ancient Latin "flumen molendinorum" title, meaning "river of mills".

It is possible to visit the mill's inner rooms and learn about the wheat flour milling process.

Archpriest's Mill

Monument in Pianto Romano

On top of the "Pianto Romano" hill, there is a memorial monument which was built to house the remains of fallen soldiers from the harsh battle of Calatafimi. This battle took place on May 15, 1860, on the western slope of the hill between Garibaldi's and Bourbon forces, marking a crucial event for the Unification of Italy. The memorial site was designed by Ernesto Basile and officially opened on May 15, 1892, to commemorate the 32nd anniversary of the battle. Its pyramidal base features some elements that recalls Classical temples. On the sides, it is decorated with two bronze groups by Battista Tassarà, which portray the landing of the Thousand in Marsala and the Battle of Calatafimi. On top, there is a towering obelisk, embellished with a bronze crown depicting the Trinacria and two palm trees. Behind the monument, the "Viale della Rimembranza" leads to a stele erected in 1960, to mark the centenary of the battle. The stele bears the famous phrase "Qui si fa l'Italia o si muore" (Here we make Italy, or we die), attributed to Garibaldi and addressed to Nino Bixio.

Every year, on May 15, the Calatafimi-Segesta Town Council commemorates the historic battle, with the attendance of local officials and people, and authorities from various parts of Italy.

Monument in Pianto Romano

Municipality of Vita

Vita is a town that lies on the slopes of Mount Baronia. It is the smallest village in the area surrounding Trapani, and the highest town in the province behind Erice. The town's foundation can be traced back to its founder, Vito Sicomo of Calatafimi (1548-1626), who held the highest offices in the Kingdom of Spain.

The town is embellished with exquisite fountains and several murals, painted by modern artists, that decorate abandoned houses' walls and doorways. The Daidone Palace, built in the late 19th century, is one of the most important buildings in Vita, also representing the local landed bourgeoisie. The most popular church is the one consecrated to the Madonna del Rosario (Our Lady of the Rosary), also referred to as the Madonna di Tagliavia, whose origins date back to a prodigious event in 1896. The present church was built in 1933. The cult for the Madonna di Tagliavia, depicted on a painting preserved in the church, has its origins in the Marian shrine of Tagliavia in Corleone, where peasants and farmers from Vita would escort their animals to be blessed. The celebration is held every year on Ascension Day. Noteworthy is also the Church of St. Francis, with its annexed convent that was then consecrated to Our Lady of the Conception, built in 1619 at the behest of Baron Vito Sicomo. Part of the convent now houses the municipality offices. Not far from the town, on the top of Mount Baronia, formerly Feudo del Sicomo, there is a 67-hectare forest consisting mainly of conifer trees. It is the perfect place for picnics, hiking, and mountain bike tours.

Municipality of Vita

Greenway DEGLI ELIMI E DEL BELICE

- SENTIERI DI
- MOBILITÀ DOLCE TRA
- STORIA, NATURA,
- TRADIZIONE E
- CONTEMPORANEITÀ

Greenway of Elymians and Belice Slow mobility trails among history, nature, tradition, and modernity

West Sicily

